

Cyber Aggression, Cyber Bullying and the Dark Triad: Effect on Workplace Behavior and Performance

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Abstract : In an increasingly connected world, where speed of communication attempts to match the speed of thought and thus intentions; conflict gets actioned faster using media like the internet and telecommunication technology. This has led to a new form of aggression: "cyber bullying". The present paper attempts to integrate existing theory on bullying, and the dark triad personality traits in a work environment and extrapolate it to the cyber context.

Keywords : conflict at work, cyber bullying, dark triad of personality, toxic employee

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